

Evaluation of certain pesticides and their alternatives against the black vine thrips, *Retithrips syriacus* (Mayet) (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) infesting grapevine

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Evaluation of certain pesticides and their alternatives against the black vine thrips, *Retithrips syriacus* (Mayet) (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) infesting grapevine

Refat OH Allam¹, Amr MMM Badawy² and Moustafa MS Bakry^{3*}

¹Faculty of Agriculture, South Valley University, Egypt

²Faculty of Science, South Valley University, Egypt

³Plant Protection Research Institute, A.R.C, Dokii, Giza, Egypt

***Corresponding Author:** Moustafa MS Bakry, Plant Protection Research Institute, A.R.C, Dokii, Giza, Egypt

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Abstract

The black vine thrips, *Retithrips syriacus* Mayet (Thripidae: Thysanoptera) is considered as pest. Adults and nymphs of this pest causes a serious damage to grapevine leaves. The experiments were carried out to evaluate the toxicity of seven pesticides on nymphs and adults of GVT on Flame seedless and Superior commercial vineyard varieties under laboratory and field conditions during 2016/2017 season. Data clearly indicate that the order of efficiency of the tested compounds were the same at both LC₅₀ and LC₉₀ levels. The tested insecticides could be descendingly arranged as follows: Radiant, Pleo, Movento, Nanoparticles Zinc oxide, Marshal, KZ oil and Garlic extract. The corresponding LC₅₀ values were 0.1, 0.24, 0.9, 0.92, 1.33, 1.45 and 1.5 ppm, while the LC₉₀ values were 0.87, 1.07, 5.48, 10.92, 8.67, 6.42 and 11.26 ppm, respectively. On the other hand, χ^2 values were 5.77, 2.93, 3.95, 3.08, 6.54, 2.87 and 1.51 respectively. Radiant had the steepest toxicity line and Garlic extract had the flattest, however Pleo, Movento, Nanoparticles Zinc oxide, Marshal and KZ oil lie in between. This reflects the superiority of Radiant and inferiority of Garlic extract. Radiant was the most toxic compound, whereas Garlic extract was the least toxic one. the initial reduction of KZ oil (71.83, 72.80, 71.50 and 70.95) in both varieties and all of them are above 70% reduction. From these results, it should be suggested using of some effective alternatives such as KZ oil for controlling black vine thrips in compatible program with chemical insecticides instead of conventional individuals' insecticides.

Keywords: Insecticides; *Retithrips syriacus*; Thrips; Grapevine

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